

branches and of spikelets on secondary branches was correlated positively with HDIPB only in parents; it was not consistent in the F₁ and F₂. HDI on secondary branches (HDISB) was correlated positively with and had direct effects on HDIPB in both segregating

(see figure) and nonsegregating generations. In most cases, negative correlations and direct and indirect effects were found between HDISB and sterility.

Higher HDI depends on more primary branches and more spikelets on

primary branches, and not on number of spikelets on secondary branches. A plant type for increased yield should have more primary branches and spikelets on primary branches, with few secondary branches and spikelets on secondary branches. □

Path diagram and coefficients of factors influencing HDIPB in F₂.

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis for high density grain index (HDI) and other rice panicle characters

S. Mallik, A. M. Aguilar, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IRRI

We assessed heterosis and heterobeltiosis for 9 quantitative characters in 6 crosses, using 6 high density (HD)-grain parents (at least 30% of grains with more than 1.20 specific gravity) and 2 low density (LD)-grain parents. HDI was calculated

as number of HD grains divided by total number of spikelets/panicle on primary (PB) and secondary (SB) branches.

Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis ($F_{mac1} - P_{mac}$) were significantly positive for number of tillers (1.74*), PB (1.27*), SB (3.28*), spikelets on PB (8.65*), spikelets on SB (8.41*), and sterility on SB (5.37*), indicating dominance of higher values. Heterosis was negative only for number of spikelets on PB (-3.01*). Low or nonsignificant heterosis for other characters may be due to little genetic

interactions or differences among parents.

The individual F₁ family differed from overall estimates for different characters showing positive, negative, or no heterosis. The F₁ means deviated conspicuously from parental and midparental values, indicating involvement of nonadditive gene action in the expression of most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction was observed in PB number, spikelets on PB, and HDI on PB and SB. Three crosses among HD-grain

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis (%) of 7 quantitative characters in 6 crosses. ^a IRRI, 1988.

Trait	H or Hb	P ₁ /P ₂ (HD/HD)	P ₃ /P ₄ (HD/HD)	P ₅ /P ₂ (HD/HD)	P ₂ /P ₆ (HD/HD)	P ₃ /P ₇ (HD/LD)	P ₂ /P ₈ (HD/LD)	LSD (0.05)
Tiller (no.)	H	25.6	2.1	11.1	13.7	-11.6	19.6	7.6
	Hb	—	-11.1	-7.4	—	-25.9	1.8	6.1
Primary branch - PB (no.)	H	28.4	-4.1	30.6	11.1	5.4	21.3	7.9
	Hb	28.3	-11.0	27.0	4.2	-8.5	12.1	9.8
Secondary branch - SB (no.)	H	29.0	-12.9	57.4	65.4	10.3	23.8	16.9
	Hb	1.1	-34.3	42.3	48.5	-18.7	10.4	18.9
Spikelet on PB (no.)	H	45.6	-7.4	56.4	19.1	-2.5	31.0	14.8
	Hb	45.4	-9.6	43.3	9.7	-7.8	19.6	13.9
Spikelet on SB (no.)	H	28.4	-16.3	49.3	72.5	-0.7	38.4	18.8
	Hb	-4.3	-38.5	21.6	46.8	-22.1	30.4	19.0
Sterility on PB (no.)	H	-28.7	87.9	-12.9	9.9	-25.7	-66.2	30.2
	Hb	-35.6	24.3	-22.6	-7.9	-27.2	-70.2	18.0
Sterility on SB (no.)	H	18.8	146.7	25.7	93.1	-15.8	-59.9	43.0
	Hb	9.0	68.7	15.9	37.2	-25.6	-65.1	27.1

^a H = heterosis, Hb = heterobeltiosis. P₁ = IR32307-75-1-3-1, P₂ = IR30, P₃ = IR34615-75-1-1, P₄ = IR29725-135-2-2-3, P₅ = IR29692-117-1-2-2, P₆ = IR35337-61-2-2-2, P₇ = IR32419-102-3-2-3, P₈ = IR32385-37-3-3-3.

Percentage of heterosis and heterobeltiosis for HDI. IRRI, 1988.

parents (P₁/P₂, P₅/P₂, P₂/P₆) and one cross between HD- and LD-grain parents (P₂/P₈) exhibited positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis for number of PB and spikelets on PB (see table). Only two crosses, P₅/P₂ and P₂/P₈,

manifested positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis for HDI on PB (see figure). The cross P₂/P₈ showed positive heterosis for all characters except sterility on PB and SB, where negative heterosis is desirable. Two crosses,

P₃/P₄ and P₃/P₇, showed negative heterosis for almost all characters.

Number of HD grains was higher on PB of parents and hybrids. Substantial heterosis for this character may lead to higher yield, since HD grains have higher test weight and higher head rice recovery. The cross P₂/P₈ had positive heterosis for all desirable traits and exceeded the highest parent for HDI on both PB and SB. □

Adaptability of rice varieties to low light intensity

M. S. Islam and M. Z. Haque, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

A major cause of low yields in the aus season in Bangladesh is low light intensity at later growth stages, mostly at ripening, due to continuous cloudy weather Jul-Aug. Wide variation in grain yield is also observed.

We studied varietal adaptability to low light intensity at ripening. Five modern and five traditional varieties were seeded so that the ripening stage would occur at the same time, late in the aus season to avoid cloudy weather. We transplanted 25-d-old seedlings in pots fertilized at 40-80-60 kg NPK/ha; 80 kg N/ha and 40 kg N/ha were topdressed in modern varieties and traditional varieties, respectively.